

FAMILY SIZE AND THE NUTRITIONAL HEALTH OF CURRICULUM USERS IN ONDO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to examine the impact of family size on nutritional health of learners in some selected communities in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. One hundred and Sixty (160) respondents were involved in the study through multi-stage random sampling. Twenty families were randomly selected from each of eight randomly selected communities in the Local Government Area. Relevant data were collected through the use of structured questionnaire and personal observation by the researcher. Data collected were analysed through simple percentages and measures of relationship using correlation coefficient of Pearson Product Movement. Results showed that 35% and 65% of the respondents eat twice and thrice daily respectively; 45% skip meals especially lunch as a result of purchasing power. There is a low relationship between family size and nutritional health as indicated in the correlation coefficient (r) 0.0153 and 0.2484. There is a moderate relationship between family size and socio economic status as indicated by (r) 0.2152 and 0.5355. It was recommended that families should have home gardens and poultry to increase consumption of fruits, vegetables and animal protein. They should also be enlightened on the importance of family planning.

Introduction

Good balanced and sufficient food is one of the essentials of life and of good healthy living. Hence, it is how well we eat good and sufficient food that tell how healthy we are and how much resistance we have to the attack of any disease (natural immunity). If one is able to eat sufficiently and adequately, all the requirements for the body's existence will be provided which can help in the proper functioning of the body organs to enable one perform adequately as required.

Sufficient and adequate food can be got when one has a reasonable number of family size that one can conveniently cater for. It is very unreasonable to keep producing children that one cannot meet their demands in terms of adequate food. It means that the children are called upon to suffer because food meant for six people would be consumed by ten or more people. The consumers cannot benefit much in such a condition. Children from large family are more liable to diseases, growth retardation and even death than those from small family.

According to Melita (1996) food can be divided into classes according to the nutrients which it contains. By eating some food from each of these classes every day, the body is provided with all it needs for normal working. Certain proportion of each nutrient is needed daily in the body to maintain health and carry out essential duties. The effect of bad feeding is most severe at the age when the child is growing and building is going on. If the number of children in the family is more than reasonable, it will be difficult to meet the demands of the food nutrients especially when the family is from the low income group. In this case, some are forced to skip one or more of the meals because of low purchasing power and large family size. This eventually leads to malnutrition when there is impairment of health, growth or physiological functioning as a result of failure in obtaining all essential nutrients in proper quantity.

Parents and caregivers greatly influence the eating environment in which children's preferences and intake patterns develop. Caregivers determine the availability and composition of a child's diet, they provide a model of eating behaviour, and guide a child's eating through feeding practices. By selecting the foods

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 that come into the home, parents have direct control over the foods to which children are repeatedly exposed. Repeated exposure to foods help determine food preference.

Statement of the Problem

It is how well we eat good and sufficient food that tells how healthy we are. However sufficient and adequate food can be got when there is a reasonable family size. If couples have more family size than they can adequately cater for there is bound to be considerable strain on the family resources and nutritional health of learners.

Research Questions

This study sought answers to the following research questions

- What is the relationship between family size and socio economic status in Ondo West Local Government area of Ondo State.
- What is the feeding pattern of families in the local government area?
- Does family size affect feeding pattern?
- How often are foods combined from various food groups?

Research Hypothesis

- Family size does not have any significant effect on nutritional health of learners.
- There is no relationship between family size and socio-economic status

Research Design and Methodology

This study made use of descriptive research design through the use of questionnaire. The study covered eight selected communities in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. These were Igbado, Igbindo, Igunsi, Bagbe, Litaye, Ita-nla, Ilu-nla and Laje communities. One hundred and sixty (160) families were selected for the study through multi-stage random sampling. The first stage was selection of eight communities and the second was random sampling of twenty (20) families from each of the eight communities. Research instruments used were twenty (20) - item structured questionnaire and observational guide. The items of the questionnaire were validated by three experts. Data was collected through one hundred and sixty questionnaires (160) administered and personal observation of the researcher. Data collected was analysed by simple percentages and measures of relationship using correlation coefficient of Pearson Product Movement.

Results

Table 1: Personal/socio-economic Data of Respondents

S/No	Test Item	No. of Response	Percentage (%)
1.	Occupation of the father		
	Farming	24	15
	Business	88	55
	Civil Servant	48	30
	Total	160	100
2.	Occupation of the mother		
	Farming	36	22.5
	Business	88	55
	Civil Servant	36	22.5
	Total	160	100
3.	Family set-up		
	Polygamous	96	60
	Monogamous	64	40
	Total	160	100

Most parents (fathers and mothers) 55% were businessmen or women. Olarewaju (2006) noted that 30% of female students of Adeyemi College of Education responded that their parents were businessmen and women. More families (60%) were polygamous while 40% were monogamous. In a polygamous home there is a higher tendency of having more children than a monogamous one.

Analysis of Data on Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

Family size does not have any significant effect on nutritional health of learners.

Table 2 – Relationship between family size and nutritional health learner

2a

Range	3-4	5-8	9-12	12-15
Family size	40	68	44	8
	25%	42.5%	27.5%	5%
Meal taken in a day	Once	Twice	Thrice	More than thrice
	0	56	104	0
	0%	35%	65%	0%

r = 0.0153

2b

Range	3-4	5-8	9-12	12-15
Family size	40	68	44	8
Type of meal skipped	Breakfast	Lunch	Supper	None
	16	48	8	88
	10%	30%	5%	55%

rule of thumb for r

r ranges from -1 through 0 to +1

+0.00 to +0.19 Neglibile

+0.20 to +0.39 Low

+0.40 to +0.59 Moderate

+0.60 to +0.79 Substantial / Appreciable

+0.80 to +0.99 High

+1 Perfect relationship

r = 0.0153 indicates low relationship

r = 0.2484 indicates low relationship

2a and 2b above shows there is little or low relationship between family size and nutritional health learners.

Also the mode of family size was 5 to 8 (42.5%) as can be seen from table 2a above. Most of the respondents (65%) ate thrice a day. 30% of those who skipped meals skipped lunch. Olarewaju 2006 noted that 56.67% of female and 25% of male students missed meals.

Hypothesis 2

There is no relationship between family size and socio-economic status.

To accept or reject this hypothesis, r was calculated from table 3a and 3b below.

Table 3 – Relationship between family size and economic status

3a.

Range	3-4	5-8	9-12	12-15
Family size	40	68	44	8
Educational Qualification	No Formal Educational 16	Primary Education 40	Secondary Education 44	Post Secondary Education 60
	10%	25%	27.5%	37.5%

3b.

Range	3-4	5-8	9-12	12-15
Family size	40	68	44	8
Occupation	Farming 24	Business 88	Civil Servant 48	Farming & Trading 36

From table 3a $r = 0.2152$, which indicates low relationship.

From table 3b $r = 0.5355$, which indicates moderate relationship.

Tables 3a and 3b shows the relationship between family size and socio economic status. The correlation coefficients show that there is low or moderate relationship between family size and socio economic status. Some (37.5%) of the respondents had post secondary education.

Hypothesis 3

Families do not combine food from various food groups? To accept or reject this hypothesis, r was calculated from Tables 4a and 4b below.

Option	Once	Twice	Thrice	More than thrice
How many times do you eat in a day?	0	56	104	0
Option	Cereals & Grains	Roots & Tubers	Fruits & Vegetable	
Milk and Milk products Do you eat from these food groups?	100 62.5%	40 25%	0 0%	20 12.5%

4b.

Option	Once	Twice	Thrice	More than thrice
How many times do you eat in a day	0	56	104	0
How often do you eat from these food groups in a day?	48 30%	100 62.5%	12 7.5%	0 0%

From Table 4a $r = 0.1023$, which indicates negligible relationship.

From Table 4b $r = 0.0044$, which indicates negligible relationship.

The result from tables 4a and 4b show that families do not combine food from various food groups. The correlation coefficients are $r = 0.1023$ and 0.0044 respectively.

The hypothesis which says families do not combine food from the various food groups is therefore accepted. Most of the respondents (62.5%) eat from the cereals and grains group and few (12.5%) eat from milk and

milk products. And none (0%) from fruits and vegetables. Olarewaju (2006) noted that 76.67% of female students of Adeyemi College of Education ate fruits and vegetables once a day.

Discussion

The result shows that there is a relationship (although low) between family size and nutritional health learners. According to Ritchie (1998), food is scarce in the house when the consumers are more than the food in the home. Because of the large family size, the members are forced to eat what they see and not what they like because the power to purchase sufficient and adequate food for the family is lacking and so the members cannot get some essential nutrients that are in other foods that they cannot purchase which is against the law of nutrition.

The result of the analysis also shows a moderate relationship between family size and socio-economic status. This indicates that socio-economic status at times can dictate the size of a family. Akman (2002) concluded that education has a major impact on fertility and that education of women stands out as a significant factor in determining fertility. The greatest impact of education on fertility occurs when levels of education are at secondary level. Most (65%) of the respondents had secondary and post secondary education. Small amounts of primary education are not likely to have a significant impact. Education has been found to increase women's levels of autonomy in decision – making, in acquiring knowledge, in gaining access to economic resources and in interacting with a wider social circle. It is through this autonomy that educational exerts an impact on fertility. A reduction in fertility rate is one of the numerous positive effects of education.

In most research studies it has been found that desired family size becomes smaller with the increase in women's educational levels (Jejeebhoy 1995), Cleland and Jejeebhoy (1996))

Preferred family size decline as educational level increases. Education is seen as a key determinant of the costs associated with fertility regulation. Education is expected to influence access to modern knowledge and ways of life. The habit of skipping or missing meals as was observed in this study will reduce nutritional status of people of this local government area. It was also observed that people (62.5% of respondents) in this area studied consumed more of cereals and grains, 0% from fruits and vegetables and 20% from milk and milk products. This habit should be improved upon as milk and milk products are very essential for children. Also fruits and vegetables should be taken by everybody.

Ekukinam (2006) said to produce healthy children, one should ensure that their food is well balanced at all times and mothers should also make sure that all food classes are present at meal time.

Conclusion

Having many children in the family affects the adequate and sufficient feeding of the family members. For example, the food that is expected to be consumed by a family of six and nutritionally beneficial to them, if taken by a family of ten or twelve people, the ration will be very low. Hence, it retards the growth of the children physically, mentally and socially.

The members of a large family with inadequate and insufficient food cannot produce antibodies which fight against disease and hence they fall victims of diseases.

Polygamous type of family gives room to unhealthy rivalry among the wives in the family, which can lead to incessant production of many children that cannot be fed sufficiently and adequately.

Because the purchasing power is low, the respondents take to buying the cheapest food stuff like cassava products with the idea that it will sustain them for longer period and this food stuff is mainly a carbohydrate food which has plenty of calories, very little protein, calcium, vitamin and iron.

It is therefore concluded based on the finding of this study that family size has an effect on the nutritinal health learners pattern of families in Ondo West Local Government Area.

Recommendation

Poor, inadequate and insufficient feeding which is predominant in some families especially the large families can do untold havoc to the physical, mental and social development of the members of the families. Hence the following recommendations are made which can help to improve the standard of living of the respondents and people generally.

- Families are encouraged to have small farm or home garden where they can plant vegetables, fruits and food crops like yam, maize, cassava, etc. excess of these crops could not be grown. Also, they can have rabbitry and poultry where they rear birds e.g cockerel, layers etc.

- People should be enlightened on the importance of family planning so that they do not go on producing children incessantly.
- Government should embark on programmes to enlighten families on the importance of good, adequate and sufficient feeding that is (balanced diet) to the development of the body.

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